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Factors responsible for the off-flavour and yellow colour in *Pangasianodon hypophthalmus*

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Over the last 20 years, production of pangasius (*Pangasianodon hypophthalmus*) in aquaculture farms in Bangladesh has significantly expanded and now contributes about 16% of the total aquaculture production of 2.3 million MT. However, pangasius cultured in Bangladesh has received less international attention than pangasius from Vietnamese fish farms. Among reasons for the limited export of Bangladeshi pangasius two important quality issues are tainting by off-flavours and yellow coloration of the flesh. The objectives of this study were to characterize off-flavour production in water of the farms and extent of off-flavours in the fish flesh, and to identify the reasons behind the yellow colouration in fish flesh. A range of studies in field ponds and experimental ponds were conducted over the last two years to assess the water quality of pangasius farmers' ponds, and to identify the reasons behind off-flavour and yellow colour in pangasius flesh by application of different water exchange frequencies and testing of various feed types in experimental ponds. The experimental work included analysis of major parameters controlling the water quality, analysis of off-flavours in pangasius flesh by GC-MS and feeds, and analysis of fish flesh by HPLC for detection of colour profiles. Two carotenoid pigments (lutein and zeaxanthin) that impart yellow or orange colour to many common foods were found in yellowish pangasius flesh. The pigments originated from different feed ingredients being used to formulate pangasius feeds. Maize is the most commonly used (5-20%) fish feed ingredient in Bangladesh, and feeds were determined to contain lutein and zeaxanthin at an amount of about 640 µg per 100 g feed. Off-flavours profiles of the fish are still being studied, but preliminary studies suggest that certain phytoplankton organisms, especially cyanobacteria, may be main responsible for the tainting, but more analyses are needed before a general conclusion can be given. A clear relation between ingredients of pangasius feed and the muscle coloration was observed. An on-going pond experiment shows that replacement of intense coloured feed ingredients to low-pigment containing feeds most likely will result in white flesh colour. Conclusions on the extent of off-flavouring of the fish await analysis at University of Copenhagen.